

**Tb³⁺ / Yb³⁺ doped aluminosilicate phosphors for near infrared emission and efficient
down-conversion**

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Abstract

The spectral mismatch between incident solar photons and the bandgap of crystalline silicon in solar cells results in major energy losses. Photons with energies lower than the bandgap are lost due to transparency, while those with energies above the bandgap value will be absorbed, generating electron-hole pairs, but consuming only the energy E_g , with the excess being lost as heat through thermalization. Despite intensive research to obtain efficient down-conversion (DC) materials for frequency shifting layers in c-Si cells, their development so far involves techniques which are not cost effective. Taking this into account, aluminosilicate phosphors co-doped with the Tb^{3+} / Yb^{3+} ion pair have been synthesized by sol-gel (SG) processing, a low cost technique which allows scalability and is especially useful to obtain films. The molar composition 90 SiO_2 -10 $AlO_{1.5}$ was chosen as host to investigate if DC based on the Tb^{3+} / Yb^{3+} pair leads to efficient quantum cutting in such material. We demonstrate the potential of this approach to obtain near infrared DC emission in aluminosilicate matrix with a conversion efficiency of up to 158%, with potential to improve the performance of low bandgap photovoltaic solar cells.

KEYWORDS: sol-gel; aluminosilicate phosphor; Tb^{3+} / Yb^{3+} pair; down-conversion

Introduction

Over the past few decades, researchers have been struggling for efficient and cost-effective conversion of solar energy into electricity through photovoltaic (PV) solar cells. With incorporation of quantum-cutting phosphors, the loss of energy due to thermalization of hot charge carriers, especially in low bandgap semiconductors like c-Si, can be minimized by the conversion of high-energy solar photons into lower energy but above bandgap photons through down-shifting and quantum cutting luminescent materials [1].

Recently, near infrared (NIR) quantum cutting has been achieved by means of lanthanide (Ln) ions [2–6], due to their rich energy level structure and high quantum efficiency of light emission. The properties of quantum-cutting luminescent materials are dependent on various factors such as the host matrix composition and structure, nature of dopant ions and their concentrations, etc. The host material, in particular, has an essential role in the luminescence properties. Effective control of the above parameters can enhance the quantum-cutting ability of the phosphor material. Crystalline Si is by far the most widely used material in PV solar cells. Therefore, it is necessary to find suitable doped luminescent layers to improve the efficiency of silicon based (low bandgap) solar cells. Among the Ln ions, the Tb^{3+} / Yb^{3+} pair represents an important sensitizer/acceptor combination for DC, due to the absorption of Tb^{3+} around 480 nm (near the maximum solar spectrum intensity) and its energy transfer to two acceptor Yb^{3+} ions which emit in the range of ~ 970-1100 nm, only slightly above the Si bandgap. Therefore, a promising system to study second-order energy transfer processes is the combination of one Tb^{3+} and two Yb^{3+} ions, where the former center, optimized for strong absorption, transfers its energy to the latter two, optimized for efficient emission, by a second-order cooperative, simultaneous quantum cutting process, rather than a first-order or sequential one. Quantum cutting emission from Tb^{3+} / Yb^{3+} pair has been studied in different host matrices. $\text{Y}_{0.74}\text{Yb}_{0.25}\text{Tb}_{0.01}\text{PO}_4$ powder, prepared by solid state reaction [7], lithium borate

glass [8] (with a quantum efficiency of 137% when doped with 1 mol% Tb³⁺ and 5 mol% Yb³⁺, under 266 and 355 nm excitation), lanthanum borogermanate glasses [9] (with quantum efficiency of 148% when doped with 0.1 mol% Tb and 0.5 mol% Yb), Tb³⁺ / Yb³⁺ co-doped transparent oxyfluoride glass ceramics containing CaF₂ nanocrystals, with molar composition 60SiO₂-20Al₂O₃-20CaF₂-0.3Tb³⁺-xYb³⁺ (quantum efficiency of 155% for 0.3 mol% Tb and 26 mol% Yb) [10] and 50SiO₂-20Al₂O₃-27CaF₂-1Tb³⁺-xYb³⁺ glass (quantum efficiency of 120% with 5% Yb³⁺ doping), synthesized by conventional melting-quenching method [11]. However, these techniques require high temperatures. In contrast, soft chemical methods (co-precipitation and SG method) or combustion synthesis have the advantage of decreased processing temperature. For example, Y_{3-x-y}Tb_xYb_yGa₅O₁₂ was prepared by solution combustion technique (with quantum efficiency of 128% for 0.01 mol% Tb³⁺ and 0.015 mol% Yb³⁺, under 379 nm excitation) [12] and Y₂O₃ powder samples were obtained by co-precipitation followed by an annealing process (the effective quantum efficiency was 137% [13] and 181% [14] with 0.01 mol% Tb³⁺/0.2 mol% Yb³⁺ and 0.1 mol% Tb³⁺/10 mol% Yb³⁺ doping, respectively, under 304 nm excitation). Regarding the luminescence measurements, these last two materials revealed enhanced properties, but the excitation was far from the maximum solar spectrum intensity (around ~ 500 nm). Glass ceramic films of molar composition 70 SiO₂ – 30 HfO₂ also appear to be a promising host obtained by SG dip-coating technique, with an effective quantum efficiency of 138% for 1 mol% Tb³⁺ and 4 mol% Yb³⁺ [15], when excited at 474 nm.

Among numerous luminescent materials for NIR emission, in this work we focus on an aluminosilicate phosphor doped with terbium and ytterbium, due to its good solubility for these ions, good chemical stability, sufficiently low phonon energies and easily synthesized at moderate temperature by SG processing, a low-cost technology that is versatile and scalable [16]. Moreover, the SG fabrication technique has the added advantage that it can easily be

coupled with the deposition of films and multilayered structures in order to integrate the spectral conversion function into more complex but more efficient structures.

Although aluminosilicate materials have been studied intensively, the preparation by SG of homogeneous multicomponent samples based on the $\text{SiO}_2 - \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ matrix still presents challenges. And in spite of many works on the luminescent properties of doped $\text{SiO}_2 - \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ matrices, a correlation between their microstructures (which may include glassy and crystalline phases simultaneously in varying proportions) and photoluminescence (PL) emission characteristics is not yet clear at present. In this work, different $\text{Tb}^{3+} / \text{Yb}^{3+}$ doped $\text{SiO}_2 - \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ mixtures were heat treated at $1100\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, followed by a detailed investigation of the phases obtained and their contribution to the luminescence properties of the active ions. The PL behavior has been studied in detail as a function of the Tb and Yb concentrations.

Methods

Materials: For the preparation of the aluminosilicate sol, the precursors were TEOS (tetraethyl orthosilicate, Alfa Aesar, 98 %) and $\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Aluminum nitrate nonahydrate, Alfa Aesar, 98.0-102.0 %); Ethanol (Merck, 99.5 %) and distilled water were used as solvents and HCl (Sigma Aldrich, 37%) was used as a catalyst. For the doped solutions, terbium and ytterbium nitrates were added in the required amounts. The samples prepared had the nominal composition (in mol %): $(90-x-y)\text{ SiO}_2 - 10\text{ AlO}_{1.5} - x\text{ TbO}_{1.5} - y\text{ YbO}_{1.5}$ ($x = 0, 1, 3, 5$ and $y = 0, 5, 10, 15$). Henceforth, all compositions in this paper are expressed in mol%.

Synthesis: As a first step, the hydrolysis of TEOS was initiated by preparing a solution composed of TEOS, water (in a molar ratio water/TEOS = 4), ethanol and HCl added in order to achieve pH = 2. After mixing, the solution was stirred and heated at approximately $70\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ during 1 h, labelled solution "A". A separate solution of Aluminum nitrate was prepared by

dissolving the required amount of the nitrate in ethanol (labelled solution “B”), which was added slowly to solution “A” while stirring. This mixed solution (labelled “C”) was then stirred for 10 minutes at 70 °C. For doped solutions, terbium and ytterbium nitrates were dissolved in the stoichiometric proportions in ethanol (solution “D”) and this was finally added to solution “C” and stirred for an additional 10 minutes at 70 °C. The final solution was aged for several days and the bulk gels obtained were heat treated at 1100 °C for 30 minutes (with heating and cooling rates of about 5 °C/min), yielding samples in the form of powders .

Structural and microstructural characterization: The presence of crystalline phases was characterized by X-ray diffraction, XRD (Philips PW 3020 diffractometer using CuK α radiation, $\lambda=1.5406\text{\AA}$ and operating at 40 mA and 30 W). Additional structural characterization was carried out by unpolarized Raman microscopy (Labram HR 800 Evolution micro-Raman spectrometer, Horiba JobinYvon, using a 532 nm diode laser for excitation and a 600 groove mm⁻¹ grating); the laser power at the samples was 10 mW and the data were collected in the range of 100–1800 cm⁻¹ at a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹ at room temperature (RT), with a 100X objective lens.

Luminescence characterization: The luminescence properties of these materials were investigated by measuring emission and excitation spectra. The PL spectra of the phosphors were recorded with a spectrofluorimeter (Fluorolog®-3-22, HORIBA Jobin Yvon) at RT, working with a continuous wave 450 W Xe lamp; a R928 Hamamatsu detector was used for visible detection and a liquid-N₂-cooled DSS-IGA020L detector (Electro-Optical Systems, Inc.) for the NIR range. The emission spectra were measured over the visible wavelength range of 500–700 nm and in the NIR range of 925–1200 nm, with excitation at $\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 484$ nm. The

experimental spectra were corrected for variations in lamp intensity over the spectral range, as well as for the excitation monochromator, emission monochromator and detector responses.

The PL decay profiles were also recorded with the same instrument, after the samples were exposed to monochromatic light of $\lambda_{exc} = 484$ nm. The signal was monitored by a Hamamatsu R928 photomultiplier tube. All PL measurements were collected at a right angle to the excitation beam.

Results & Discussion

Figures 1 (a-c) show the XRD patterns of the samples with different dopant concentrations treated at 1100 °C during 30 minutes. While the sample with 1% Tb³⁺ is essentially amorphous, with no distinct diffraction peaks, an increase in the Tb concentration up to 3 or 5% causes a distinct diffraction peak to appear at $2\theta \sim 21.87^\circ$, which can be assigned to cristobalite SiO₂. It is known that there are two polymorphs of cristobalite, the high-temperature β -phase (cubic symmetry) and the low temperature α -phase (tetragonal symmetry) [17]. The α -polymorph patterns are characterized by a peak at $2\theta = 21.6^\circ$ (JCPDS No. 04-0379), while the β -polymorph exhibits a main peak at $2\theta = 21.98^\circ$ (JCPDS No. 27-0605). The peak around $2\theta = 36^\circ$ could attributed to reflection from the (220) planes of β -cristobalite, corresponding to $2\theta = 35.627^\circ$, or to the reflections from (200) and (112) planes of α -cristobalite, corresponding to $2\theta = 36.056^\circ$ and 36.373° , respectively. In addition, cristobalite also appeared in the samples doped with 1 or 3% Tb³⁺ and co-doped with 5 and 10% Yb³⁺. On the other hand, the samples with 1 and 3% Tb³⁺ plus 15% Yb³⁺ show diffraction peaks related to β -Yb₂Si₂O₇ (JCPDS card 00-030-1440), while samples with 5% Tb³⁺ plus 5, 10 or 15% Yb³⁺ have diffraction peaks assigned to β -Yb₂Si₂O₇, but not to cristobalite. Therefore, the

formation of β - $\text{Yb}_2\text{Si}_2\text{O}_7$ is favored at high $[\text{Yb}^{3+}] = 15\%$, or even by Yb^{3+} contents $< 15\%$ (5 or 10%), if the $[\text{Tb}^{3+}] = 5\%$.

Ln silicate systems have great interest for laser materials and phosphors. Despite the similar radii of Y^{3+} and Yb^{3+} ions, while there are seven different polymorphs reported for $\text{Y}_2\text{Si}_2\text{O}_7$, namely α , β , γ , δ , ϵ , ζ and η , there is only a β -polymorph known for $\text{Yb}_2\text{Si}_2\text{O}_7$ [14]. Although we have not been able to assess what are the fractions of the crystalline and amorphous phases present in each case, the absence of an amorphous halo at $\sim 22^\circ$ suggests that the co-doped samples with 15% Yb^{3+} , or those with 5% Tb^{3+} and 5 or 10% Yb^{3+} , are formed mostly by β - $\text{Yb}_2\text{Si}_2\text{O}_7$ and possibly an aluminosilicate phase which could not be identified. It is not possible at present to determine whether all the Yb^{3+} ions are incorporated into the β - $\text{Yb}_2\text{Si}_2\text{O}_7$ phase, or to specify the structural positions of the Tb^{3+} ions. Some additional information will come from the PL measurements given below.

Raman microscopy has also been used for monitoring the phase evolution in the present Ln aluminosilicate system. The unpolarized Raman spectra of samples in the $(90-x-y)$ SiO_2 -10 $\text{AlO}_{1.5}$ - x $\text{TbO}_{1.5}$ - y $\text{YbO}_{1.5}$ ($x = 0, 1, 3, 5$ and $y = 0, 5, 10, 15$) system, heat treated at 1100 °C, are shown in **Figures 2 (a-c)**. Despite some narrow peaks in the $\sim 700 - 900 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ range, the spectra of the single-doped samples with 1, 3 or 5% Tb^{3+} and those co-doped with 1 Tb^{3+} / 5 Yb^{3+} and 3 Tb^{3+} / 5 Yb^{3+} suggest a major amorphous character and appear to agree with the XRD results. The Raman mode at $\sim 410 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ may be assigned to Si-O-Si symmetric stretching (SS) vibrations of the high silica glass network, involving motions of the bridging oxygens only, like in pure silica glass [18]. The weak peaks at ~ 486 and 600 cm^{-1} are usually assigned in pure silica glass to defect modes involving 4- and 3-membered silicate rings, respectively [18–20]. Although XRD did not show the presence of the β - $\text{Yb}_2\text{Si}_2\text{O}_7$ phase in samples with 1 Tb^{3+} / 10 Yb^{3+} and 3 Tb^{3+} / 10 Yb^{3+} , the corresponding Raman spectra show modes which can be attributed to the presence of this phase. Comparing with literature

assignments for a similar structure, β - $\text{Y}_2\text{Si}_2\text{O}_7$, which presents Raman peaks at 185, 285, 365, 430, 520 and 665 cm^{-1} , plus a double peak at 920 / 960 cm^{-1} [21], the bands observed in the spectra of co-doped samples with 1 Tb^{3+} / (10 and 15) Yb^{3+} and 3 Tb^{3+} / (10 and 15) Yb^{3+} at 145, 274, 370, 415, 520 and 670 cm^{-1} , plus the distinctive doublet at 925 / 955 cm^{-1} , can be assigned to specific vibrational modes of β - $\text{Yb}_2\text{Si}_2\text{O}_7$. The observed red shifts are due to the higher mass of Yb (173.054) compared to Y (88.906) and show the influence of the Yb^{3+} ions on the vibrations corresponding to these Raman peaks [23]. Although only the β -polymorph is known for the $\text{Yb}_2\text{Si}_2\text{O}_7$ phase [14], the spectrum of the sample co-doped with 5 Tb^{3+} / 15 Yb^{3+} shows a different Raman signature which quite resembles the Raman spectrum of δ - $\text{Y}_2\text{Si}_2\text{O}_7$ [22] and can tentatively be attributed to specific vibrational modes of δ - $\text{Yb}_2\text{Si}_2\text{O}_7$. Regarding the 5 Tb^{3+} / 5 and 10 Yb^{3+} samples, both β - $\text{Yb}_2\text{Si}_2\text{O}_7$ and δ - $\text{Yb}_2\text{Si}_2\text{O}_7$ phases seem to coexist, together with an amorphous aluminosilicate phase.

Figure 1. XRD patterns of aluminosilicate powder samples heat treated at 1100 °C and doped with: **(a)** 1% Tb and 0, 5, 10 and 15 % Yb; **(b)** 3% Tb and 0, 5, 10 and 15% Yb; **(c)** 5% Tb and 0, 5, 10 and 15% Yb.

Figure 2. Raman spectra of aluminosilicate powder samples heat treated at 1100 °C in the range of 100 to 1800 cm^{-1} , doped with: **(a)** 1% Tb and 0, 5, 10 and 15 % Yb; **(b)** 3% Tb and 0, 5, 10 and 15% Yb; **(c)** 5% Tb and 0, 5, 10 and 15% Yb.

Figures 3 (a-c) depict the PL spectra of samples doped with 1, 3 or 5% Tb and different Yb contents (5, 10 and 15%) under 484 nm excitation. Each figure shows narrow emission bands resulting from $4f \rightarrow 4f$ transitions within Tb^{3+} , with the most intense peak at 542 nm corresponding to the $^5\text{D}_4 \rightarrow ^7\text{F}_5$ transition. Five other peaks are observed, at 584 nm ($^5\text{D}_4 \rightarrow ^7\text{F}_4$), 620 nm ($^5\text{D}_4 \rightarrow ^7\text{F}_3$), 655 nm ($^5\text{D}_4 \rightarrow ^7\text{F}_2$), 667nm ($^5\text{D}_4 \rightarrow ^7\text{F}_1$) and 677nm ($^5\text{D}_4 \rightarrow ^7\text{F}_0$) [23,24]. The emission intensity increases with the Tb^{3+} content from 1 to 5%, but, for the same Tb content, it decreases with the introduction of Yb^{3+} due to $\text{Tb}^{3+} \rightarrow \text{Yb}^{3+}$ energy transfer.

Figures 3 (d-f) illustrate the excitation spectra monitored at $\lambda_{em} = 542$ nm. The excitation peaks at 484, 376, 367, 350, 340, 318, 302 and 282 nm can be attributed to the transitions from the $^7\text{F}_6$ ground state to $^5\text{D}_4$, ($^5\text{D}_3 + ^5\text{G}_6$), $^5\text{L}_{10}$, $^5\text{G}_5$, $^5\text{L}_7$, $^5\text{H}_7$, $^5\text{H}_6$ and $^5\text{I}_8$ states, respectively [25]. The width of the Tb^{3+} PL peaks upon excitation at 484 nm (Figures 3 (a-c)) suggests that most Tb^{3+} ions are probably located within an amorphous aluminosilicate environment. In fact, a pure silica crystalline phase like cristobalite, for example, is expected to have rather limited solubility for Ln ions like Tb^{3+} or Yb^{3+} .

Figure 3. Photoluminescence spectra in the visible range of aluminosilicate powder samples treated at 1100 °C, doped with: **(a)** 1% Tb and 0, 5, 10 and 15% Yb; **(b)** 3% Tb and 0, 5, 10 and 15% Yb; **(c)** 5% Tb and 0, 5, 10 and 15% Yb, under 484 nm excitation. Excitation spectra of aluminosilicate samples doped with: **(d)** 1% Tb and 0, 5, 10 and 15% Yb; **(e)** 3% Tb and 0, 5, 10 and 15% Yb; **(f)** 5% Tb and 0, 5, 10 and 15% Yb, monitored at λ_{em} 542 nm.

Figure 4 shows PL spectra in the NIR under 484 nm excitation. Three main Yb³⁺ emission bands are observed in the NIR at 978, ~ 1001-1017 and 1034 nm. These peaks originate from 1 Tb³⁺ (⁵D₄) → 2 Yb³⁺ (²F_{5/2}) non-radiative energy transfer, followed by quantum cutting DC radiative emission 2 Yb³⁺ (²F_{5/2}) → 2 Yb³⁺ (²F_{7/2}) at ~ 1000 nm.

Figure 5 shows a detailed energy level diagram of Tb³⁺ and Yb³⁺. Under UV and blue excitation, both visible emissions corresponding to Tb³⁺ ⁵D₄ → ⁷F_J transitions and NIR emissions within 950 -1100nm were observed. The excitation spectra of Tb³⁺ consist of strong 4f-5d bands within the 250-368 nm range and the ⁷F₆ → ⁵D_J (J = 3,4) transitions at around

377 and 484 nm are in agreement with the electronic energy levels of Tb^{3+} . As shown in **Figure 5**, Yb^{3+} has only an excited state (triplet) level at around 980 nm. Since direct excitation at 484 nm is far from resonance with Yb^{3+} at ~ 980 nm and the visible emission intensity decreases with the introduction of Yb^{3+} , these facts undoubtedly prove the occurrence of energy transfer from $Tb^{3+} \rightarrow Yb^{3+}$. It can also be observed that the PL intensity in the NIR (which is ~ 0 for 0% Yb) generally increases with the Yb^{3+} content in the samples with 1% Tb^{3+} , whereas for those with 3 and 5% Tb^{3+} the emission intensity reaches a maximum at 10% Yb^{3+} and then gradually decreases due to concentration quenching. The increase in the degree of Stark splitting for samples with 10 and 15 mol% Yb, compared to those with 5% Yb, is in general agreement with the preferential presence of Yb^{3+} ions within the β - $Yb_2Si_2O_7$ crystalline phase in the former. **Figure 4** shows also additional emission peaks at 1071 (weak), 1086 and 1096 nm. In the literature, these have not been observed. However, most previous studies employed a CCD with a detection limit of ~ 1060 nm [8,12,14,26], while other works show a broad band extending until 1100 nm [9–11,27–30]. Only one study showed an emission peak at 1070 nm [13]. These artifact peaks can be assigned to second order effects at twice the wavelength of the visible luminescence peaks.

Figure 4. Photoluminescence spectra in the NIR range of doped aluminosilicate powder samples treated at 1100 °C, doped with: **(a)** 1% Tb and 0, 5, 10 and 15% Yb; **(b)** 3% Tb and 0, 5, 10 and 15% Yb; **(c)** 5% Tb and 0, 5, 10 and 15% Yb, under 484 nm excitation.

Figure 5. Schematic electronic energy level diagram of Tb³⁺ and Yb³⁺, showing the co-operative energy transfer mechanism Tb³⁺ (⁵D₄) → 2 Yb³⁺ (²F_{5/2})

In order to further establish the nature of the energy transfer process, lifetime measurements were carried out for the different aluminosilicate compositions (**Figures 6 (a-c)**). According to the literature [11,20], the PL decay time (or 1/e lifetime) for the ⁵D₄ level of Tb³⁺ is between ~

2-3 ms. For the single doped aluminosilicate samples with 1, 3 and 5% Tb, which are seen to exhibit basically single exponential decays, the determined lifetimes were 2.37, 2.16 and 2.02 ms, respectively, within the expected range of values. As the Yb³⁺ content increased from 0 to 15%, faster decays were observed, with non-single exponential behavior, suggesting significant energy transfer from Tb³⁺ (⁵D₄) → Yb³⁺ (²F_{5/2}), with different rates for Tb³⁺ / Yb³⁺ ion pairs in varying structural environments. In these cases, the average lifetime was computed according to $\bar{\tau} = \int t I(t)dt / \int I(t)dt$

Figure 6. Experimental PL decay curves of aluminosilicate powder samples for $\lambda_{exc}=484$ nm and $\lambda_{em}=542$ nm. Samples doped with: **(a)** 1% Tb and 0, 5, 10 and 15% Yb; **(b)** 3% Tb and 0, 5, 10 and 15% Yb; **(c)** 5% Tb and 0, 5, 10 and 15% Yb.

The energy transfer efficiency from Tb³⁺ (⁵D₄) → Yb³⁺ (²F_{5/2}), $\eta_{xTb, yYb}$, as well as the effective quantum efficiency, $\eta_{EQE(xTb, yYb)}$, defined as the ratio between the number of emitted and absorbed photons, could be estimated¹⁹ from equations (1) and (2):

$$\eta_{xTb, yYb} = 1 - \frac{\int I_{xTb, yYb} dt}{\int I_{xTb} dt} \quad (\text{eq. 1})$$

$$\eta_{EQE(xTb, yYb)} = \eta_{Tb, rad} (1 - \eta_{xTb, yYb}) + 2 \eta_{xTb, yYb} \quad (\text{eq. 2})$$

where I denotes the PL intensity and xTb, yYb stands for the Tb and Yb concentrations. The relation between $\eta_{EQE(xTb, yYb)}$ and $\eta_{xTb, yYb}$, when the quantum efficiency for Tb^{3+} ions, $\eta_{Tb,rad}$, is set = 1 (assuming there are no competing non-radiative transitions), becomes simply $\eta_{EQE(xTb, yYb)} = 1 + \eta_{xTb, yYb}$. The Tb^{3+} excited state lifetimes, plus the values of $\eta_{xTb, yYb}$ and $\eta_{EQE(xTb, yYb)}$ for different concentrations of Tb^{3+} and Yb^{3+} , with 484 nm excitation, are given in Table 1 and the effective quantum efficiencies are comparable with values in the range of ~ 120 – 181% which have been obtained with different concentrations of Tb and Yb for various host matrices⁷⁻¹⁵. The values given in Table 1 generally increased with increasing Yb^{3+} concentration until 10%, but decreased beyond that. The value of $\eta_{EQE(xTb, yYb)}$ was largest for samples with 10% Yb, except for those with 3% Tb, in agreement with the strong NIR emission from those samples.

Since the energy difference between the 5D_4 (Tb^{3+}) and $^2F_{5/2}$ (Yb^{3+}) levels is rather large (~ 10,500 cm^{-1}), making the overlap integrals quite small and multiphonon relaxation essentially negligible and given the effective quantum efficiency values > 150% in most cases, simple down-shifting appears practically impossible, leading to the conclusion that one must be in the presence of a co-operative, second-order DC phenomenon, or quantum cutting, where the donor (Tb^{3+}) in fact excites two acceptor (Yb^{3+}) ions simultaneously, according to the mechanism $Tb^{3+} (^5D_4) \rightarrow 2 Yb^{3+} (^2F_{5/2})$.

Table 1. Lifetimes of Tb³⁺ (⁵D₄) in the absence and presence of Yb³⁺ ions and estimated values of Tb³⁺ (⁵D₄) → Yb³⁺ (²F_{5/2}) energy transfer efficiency and effective quantum efficiency of aluminosilicate samples with varying concentrations of Tb³⁺ and Yb³⁺ ions.

%Tb	%Yb	$\bar{\tau}$ (ms)	$\eta_{xTb, yYb}$	$\eta_{EQE(xTb, yYb)}$
1	-	2.37	-	-
1	5	1.34	0.43	1.43
1	10	1.06	0.55	1.55
1	15	1.00	0.53	1.53
3	-	2.16	-	-
3	5	0.90	0.58	1.58
3	10	0.93	0.56	1.56
3	15	0.98	0.54	1.54
5	-	2.02	-	-
5	5	1.01	0.50	1.50
5	10	0.82	0.59	1.59
5	15	0.84	0.58	1.58

Conclusions

The synthesis of aluminosilicate glasses or partially crystallized glasses doped with the sensitizer / acceptor pair Tb / Yb was carried out using SG processing, a low-cost versatile technology. Structural characterization revealed, in addition to an aluminosilicate amorphous phase, the coexistence of β -Yb₂Si₂O₇ and cristobalite secondary crystalline phases. The doped aluminosilicate materials show broad excitation spectra for emission at 542 nm, ranging from ~ 250 to 380 nm; under 484 nm excitation, NIR PL peaks are observed, corresponding to a second order process involving Tb³⁺ (⁵D₄) → 2 Yb³⁺ (²F_{5/2}) non-radiative energy transfer, followed by quantum cutting DC radiative emission 2 Yb³⁺ (²F_{5/2}) → 2 Yb³⁺ (²F_{7/2}) at ~ 1000 nm. The Tb³⁺ → Yb³⁺ energy transfer efficiency was as high as 59%, leading to Effective Quantum Efficiencies above 150%. This emission is potentially favorable to make more efficient use of the maximum intensity of the solar spectrum through frequency shifting. Therefore, the present materials are good candidates for application in PV solar cell devices.

Acknowledgments

The authors express their thanks to Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia (FCT) for financial support through project COFRE (PTDC/CTM-ENE/1087/2014).

Author contributions

The different samples were prepared by R.E.R-H. Characterization of these samples was performed by R.E.R-H, R.M.A and L.F.S., who co-operated carefully on characterization and analysis. R.E.R-H collaborated specifically on Photoluminescence characterization. The manuscript was written by R.E.R-H., edited by. R.M.A and L.F.S. and approved by all authors. All authors contributed to discussions and reviewed the manuscript.

Additional information

Competing financial interests: The authors declare no competing financial interests.

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